

DRIED FRUITS AND FINE DRIED FRUITS

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Annotation: The water content is removed from fruits by natural drying or by using special fruit dryers. Dried fruit has a long tradition of use dating back to the fourth millennium BC in Mesopotamia and is prized for its sweet taste, nutritional value and long shelf life.

Key words: Citrus fruits, storage, temperature, humidity, initial quality, storage.

Today, fruit drying is widespread. Almost half of the products sold are raisins, dates, prunes, figs, apricots, peaches, apples and pears. They are referred to as "regular" or "traditional", which have been dried in the sun or in special wind tunnels. Many fruits such as cranberries, blueberries, cherries, strawberries and mangoes are soaked in sweeteners (such as sucrose syrup) before being dried. Some foods are sold as dried fruits, such as bananas, papayas, kiwis and pineapples.

They also include nuts: walnuts, almonds, cashews, pecans, pistachios, Brazil nuts, hazelnuts, seeds, pine nuts, peanuts, corn nuts, pumpkin seeds, soy nuts and they retain most of the nutrients of fresh fruit. They all provide essential nutrients and a host of bioactive ingredients, making them a valuable tool for improving diet quality and helping to reduce the risk of chronic disease.

These foods can be whole (eg grapes, berries, apricots, plums) or pieces of fruit (eg mangoes, papayas, kiwis, bananas). The residual water content can vary from 3 - 8% to a significant 16 - 18%, depending on the type of fruit. Fruit can also be dried as a puree or as a powder. Also use the type of drying - sublimation (freeze drying). Fresh fruits are frozen and placed in a drying chamber under vacuum. Heat is applied and the water evaporates from the fruit while the fruit is still frozen. The fruit becomes very light and crispy and retains much of its original flavor.

They are widely used in confectionery and baked goods. Food manufacturers use these products in a variety of sauces, soups, marinades, side dishes, puddings, and foods for infants and children.

For better nutrient retention in dry foods, store in a cool, dark, dry place and use within a year.

Apple. Apples are high in phytonutrients (a natural component of plants that provide nutrition) that act as antioxidants, ridding the body of cancer-causing free radicals. They are also an excellent source of fiber.

Apricot. A good source of fiber, they also contain vitamin A, C and iron.

Mango. Exotic fruit, little sold in Russia. Mango is rich in various vitamins A, C and E, as well as omega-3 and 6 fatty acids, which are essential for healthy skin and the immune system.

Cherry. Compared to other fruits, they have significantly higher levels of antioxidants, as well as important nutrients such as beta-carotene, folic acid, and fiber.

Papaya. Exotic fruit, also not sold in Russia. Called the "fruit of the angels" by Christopher Columbus, papaya is an excellent source of antioxidants. Recent studies have shown that they may help prevent diabetic heart disease.

Blueberry. Blueberries also contain vitamins A, E and B, which are essential for maintaining a healthy nervous system.

Raisin. Raisins are cholesterol-free, low in sodium, high in fiber and completely defatted.

Black currant. Blackcurrants are low in saturated fat, cholesterol, and sodium and are high in vitamin C, manganese, iron, and potassium.

Plum. Such plums are called prunes. They are an excellent source of vitamins and have the added benefit of regulating the digestive system.

Pear. Pears are a good source of vitamin C and copper, and are full of dietary fiber.

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